

[View on GitHub](#)

Federated Authorization for Distributed Scientific Computing

SciToken Claims and Scopes Language

Each SciToken has one or more claim associated with it. These claims are typically used to indicate the authorizations the SciToken bearer may have – but other use cases exist (such as adding monitoring or auditing information into the token chain).

In this document, we outline the claims language utilized by SciTokens. Inherent to the SciTokens concept is flexibility: each deployment of SciTokens can add domain-specific claims for their own use cases.

Standard Claims

As a SciToken is a [JSON Web Token](#) at its base, we inherit a specific claims language from [RFC 7519](#). In this section, we outline the SciTokens-specific usage of the claims, denoting any changes in claim criticality.

- *sub* (Subject): Typically indicates the individual or entity this token was originally issued to. The subject is considered to be locally unique in the context of the VO. Usage of this claim is **OPTIONAL**. The token validators **SHOULD NOT** utilize the subject for authorization or identity mapping. Suggested use cases are auditing, monitoring, or tracing. Due to privacy concerns, some VOs may issue non-human-readable subjects or multiple anonymized subjects per individual. A VO **MUST NOT** use the same subject for multiple individuals.
- *nbf* (Not Before): The interpretation for *nbf* is unchanged from the RFC, but this is considered a **CRITICAL** attribute for a SciToken.
- *exp* (Expiration Time): The interpretation for *exp* is unchanged from the RFC, but this is considered a **CRITICAL** attribute for a SciToken. The motivation behind the combination of *nbf* and *exp* being marked as critical is to allow resources to enforce maximum token lifetime limits.
- *iss* (Issuer): The issuer of the SciTokens; this **MUST** be populated in a token chain. It **MUST** contain a unique URL for the organization; this unique key will later be used for validation and bootstrapping trust roots. This is used to identify the virtual organization (VO) that issues the token; it is expected that services maintain a map of issuer URLs to coarse-grained authorizations.
- *aud* (Audience): A service the SciToken is authorized to access. For example, if the VO has write access to several storage services, this claim may be utilized to limit a token to a single endpoint URI. As in RFC7519, the *aud* claim is not necessarily a URI: for example, it might be the name of a target site. The service may accept several different possible audiences; the service endpoint at `https://storage.example.com` may accept an audience of either `Site_Example` or `https://storage.example.com`

but ought to reject an audience of `https://www.google.com`. Additionally, the `aud` can be a special value of `ANY`, where it would allow any audience to match. The `aud` claim is `OPTIONAL` in version 1.0, mandatory in 2.0.

Client	Server	Result
ANY	ANY	Error
ANY	example.com	Success
example.com	ANY	Error
example.com	example.com	Success
notwork.com	example.com	Fail

The server cannot apply `ANY`, as that is invalid.

- *jti* (JWT ID): The interpretation for `jti` is unchanged from the RFC. It is a unique identifier that protects against replay attacks, improves traceability of tokens through a distributed system, and enables revocation. The `jti` claim is `OPTIONAL`.
- *ver* (Version): The version of the token. `ver` is used to version the claim formats and attribute names. The format of the `ver` claim is: `<profile>:<version>`. The `ver` claim is optional in SciTokens 1.0 but mandatory in all other versions; if absent, clients **MUST** process the token as belonging to the SciTokens 1.0 profile

SciToken Claim Semantics

The SciTokens project defines JWT claims behavior specific to our problem domain. From RFC 7519:

A producer and consumer of a JWT **MAY** agree to use Claim Names that are Private Names: names that are not Registered Claim Names (Section 4.1) or Public Claim Names (Section 4.2). Unlike Public Claim Names, Private Claim Names are subject to collision and should be used with caution.

Currently, the SciTokens domain-specific claims include:

- *scope*: A JSON string containing a space-separated list of scopes associated with this token, in the format described in Section 3.3 of [RFC 6749](#)[RFC6749]. For SciTokens, we aim to define a common set of storage authorizations, but envision additional authorizations will be added to meet new use cases. The interpretation of this is a list of operations the bearer is allowed to perform. Known authorizations are:
 - `read`: Read data from a resource.
 - `write`: Write data from a resource.
 - `queue`: Submit a task or a job to a queueing service.
 - `execute`: Immediately launch or execute a task.

The operation definitions are currently kept open-ended and intended to be interpreted by the specific user community.

SciTokens scopes may additionally provide a resource path, which further limits the authorization. These paths are provided in the form `$AUTHZ:$PATH`. For example, the scope `read:/foo` would provide a read authorization for the resource at `/foo` but not `/bar`. Resources allow a hierarchical relationship to

be expressed; an authorization for `write:/baz` implies a write authorization for the resources at `/baz/qux`. Resources accepting SciTokens MUST handle these resource-based authorizations.

For read and write scopes, `$PATH` must be specified; if not specified in the scope, the path may be assumed to be `.`. When examining the contents of this attribute, paths *must* be normalized according to [section 6 of RFC 3986](#). Hence, `///foo/bar/./baz` and `/foo/baz` are considered the same path for the purpose of determining access permissions. As in RFC 3986, each component of the path must be URL-escaped.

The scope claim is REQUIRED.

SciTokens Scopes

The claims language defined by JWT is based on JSON, making it extremely flexible. However, when creating an authorization token using the OAuth2 protocol, the client may only provide a space-delimited set of scopes; it is up to the authorization server to generate an appropriate SciToken with a list of claims. SciTokens aims to standardize a set of scopes and the corresponding mapping to claims.

- `aud:NAME`. Use this scope to request an audience claim for `NAME` in the returned authorization token. Multiple `aud` scopes may be given.
- `AUTHZ:PATH`. Use this scope to request authorization against a given resource.

The server-side parsing of scopes should follow [Section 3.3 of RFC6749](#).

A server MUST NOT return tokens with more authorization granted than requested. For example, if the client requests the following scopes:

```
read:/foo write:/foo/subdir
```

the server MAY return a token containing the following:

```
{
  ...
  "scope": "read:/foo/subdir write:/foo/subdir"
  ...
}
```

Example JWT

Suppose we would like to sign the following JWT header and payload:

```
{
  "alg": "RS256",
  "typ": "JWT"
}
{
  "sub": "bbockelm",
  "exp": 1509991790,
  "iss": "https://scitokens.org/cms",
  "iat": 1509988190,
  "scope": "read:/store write:/store/user/bbockelm",
  "nbf": 1509988190,
  "ver": "scitoken:2.0",
  "aud": "https://transfer-server.example.com"
```

```
}
```

Then, the corresponding base64-encoded and signed payload would be (line breaks are given only for clarity; should not be included in the actual token):

```
eyJhbGciOiJSUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IkpXVCJ9.eyJzdWIiOiJiYm9ja2VsbSI6ImV4cCI6MTUwOTk5MTc5MCwiaXNzIjoiaHR0cHM6Ly9zY2l0b2t1bnMub3JnL2NtcyIsIm1hdCI6MTUwOTk4ODE5MCwic2NvcGUiOiJyZWZkOi9zdG9yZSB3cm10ZTovc3RvcmludXNlci9iYm9ja2VsbSI6Im5iZiI6MTUwOTk4ODE5MCwidmVyIjoic2NpdG9rZW46Mi4wIiwiaXVkiIjoiaHR0cHM6Ly9jbXMuZXhhbXBsZS5jb20ifQ.fCtyZQQNPaowQ5FXFVI1bt2Qpb4ui8Bk11qXpwLKI3FQ0AKP640zf7NLKI8nRHAAqh9XRQAx89YtAJAeHriSN422-CraARoYyBdrZMtwlXph0LPkpubIusVYB3r4zIRt4BoB7NlqLqwVV2e5rGtKJGvi9tpY2FNr7eZ6eBrzAg
```

Examples SciToken scope

In this section, we only show the token payload, not base64-encoded, and remove the standard claims in order to improve readability.

Suppose we have two token-issuing services, `https://cms.cern/oauth` for the CMS organization and `https://ligo.org/oauth` for LIGO.

A LIGO user who can read any LIGO file may need the following token:

```
{
  "scope": "read:/",
  "iss": "https://ligo.org/oauth"
}
```

This is equivalent to the following URI-form:

```
{
  "scope": "https://scitokens.org/v1/authz/read:/",
  "iss": "https://ligo.org/oauth"
}
```

Note that the resource in the `scope` claim is implicitly relative to a base authorization for the LIGO organization. Here, `/` allows access to all LIGO files, *not* all files in the storage service.

To stageout to `/store/user/bbockel`, a part of the CMS namespace at the CMS site `T2_US_Nebraska`, a user would utilize the following token:

```
{
  "scope": "write:/store/user/bbockel",
  "iss": "https://cms.cern/oauth",
}
```

The `aud` claim must be used to restrict a token to a specific endpoint:

```
{
  "scope": "write:/store/user/bbockel",
  "iss": "https://cms.cern/oauth",
  "aud": "https://transfer.unl.edu"
}
```

This material is based upon work supported by the National Science Foundation under Grant No. [1738962](#). Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this material are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the views of the National Science Foundation.